

Xerophyta viscosa

Small black-stick lily

© M. Prag

Group: Monocot

Size: 0.3 to 0.5m tall.

Distribution:

Distribution includes the Namibia, Free State, KwaZulu-Natal, Lesotho, and Swaziland.

Importance:

Xerophyta species are desiccation tolerant, with leaves able to survive dehydration to below 5% relative water content. To identify the regulatory switches that protect against desiccation, multiple *Xerophyta* genomes can be compared. Although a genome assembly attributed to *X. viscosa* has been published, it is actually that of *X. schlechteri*; assembling the true *X. viscosa* genome will correct this and help identify conserved regulatory switches.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 105.33 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 11.21 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 0.46 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.4% [Single: 79.1%, Duplicated: 19.3%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 127.85 kilobases

Contig number: 8 626

Sample Contributor contact details:

Nicola Illing

University of Cape Town

nicola.illing@uct.ac.za